

Horror without Monsters: A Carrollian Reading of Daniel Handler's A Series of Unfortunate Events

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Abstract:

By using Noel Carroll's theory of art-horror this paper studies how horror functions in Daniel Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events*. The series creates a continuous and strong feeling of fear that works beyond a normal children's adventure story, although it is usually described as children's gothic fiction. Noel Carroll opines that horror creates if a character is both dangerous and impure. Using Carroll's idea, the paper explains that a character Count Olaf is not only a villain but also an immoral human that has monstrous nature. He is not a supernatural monster as we read in gothic fictions. He is a bad person in the story. He does wrong things on purpose. He works against children. But the important thing here is that his impurity does not come from his physically unnaturalness, but from his unethical actions and his misuse of social roles such as guardian of the Baudelaire children or authority figure in the family.

Count Olaf repeatedly gets failure of adults in the series and he tries to do villainous actions again and again that increases the sense of horror in the story. The problem is not only the character Olaf as a villain, but also the larger system that includes the people who come as the guardian of the children after their parent's death. They all fail to protect children. The paper shows that Handler has reshaped horror for young readers by the connecting it to ideas from Gothic novels. It also becomes a form of social criticism because it reflects dark irony, and unstable social structures that operate throughout the series. Daniel Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events* proves that always horror does not need supernatural creatures like God, Goddess, deity, fairies and ghosts or souls. If the characters from the novel are corrupted and immoral, their moral corruption and activities of social breakdown create fear or horror. Noel Carroll's theory explains the horror that can be understood as a modern form of horror that describes monstrosity in the ethical world rather than in the paranormal that cannot be explained by science or normal nature of laws.

Introduction:

Daniel Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events* occupies a special and unusual place within children's literature. The series focuses again and again on pain, moral confusion and dishonesty, however it is written for the children. The story highlights the weakness and failure of children while facing the corrupted guardians like Count Olaf who lives as a high class person in the social systems. Instead of giving comfort or a happy feeling as other children stories it rises up

tensions and worries and horror throughout the series. As the series reflects this dark tone, the it can be studied using Noel Carroll's theory of art-horror.

Theoretical Framework:

In his book *The Philosophy of Horror*, Noel Carroll explains horror as a strong emotional reaction to characters that is created through both the factors like fear and disgust (15–16). According to him monsters are dangerous and

impure because they disturb normal social and cultural rules (43). Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events* does not include ghosts or supernatural beings, but it creates a similar feeling of horror through immoral actions of the guardian Count Olaf who breakdowns the rules and morality of family institutions and creates horror in the story. Noel Carroll's idea of art-horror mainly applicable to supernatural monsters in the gothic fiction, however, when we apply his theory to children's literature especially to Daniel handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events*, we find an important new development that his theory functions here. Noel Carroll usually connects impurity with unnatural beings such as ghosts, spirits, vampires, zombies, or mixed creatures (Carroll 32), but *A Series of Unfortunate Events* shows that such impurity can also exist in social systems and immoral behavior of the characters.

Count Olaf does not break natural or biological rules. Instead, he destroys the moral difference between a protector who has the responsibility of Baudelaire as a guardian and a criminal who does several crimes to get an estate and money. So his all activities proves him a monster who is corrupted and immoral too. This change shows that Noel Carrol's theory of art-horror can relates to the works that do not include ghosts or supernatural beings. In the case of *A Series of Unfortunate Events*, the "monster" is not outside the society; it exists within social institution such as family. This new reading expands Carroll's theory. If horror depends on breaking normal categories (43), then corruption in institutions can also be a true form of impurity. In Handler's story, monstrosity moves from the frightening body of Count Olaf to his failure of social and bureaucratic systems. This shift reflects and creates modern fears about authority and loss of trust that children possess in the family from their guardians or parents.

Daniel Handler has placed horror inside unstable social systems so his series connects with what Fred Botting calls the Gothic's engagement with cultural fears (Botting 2). As in Gothic stories the fear in this story does not come from haunted houses, but from guardians and authorities who fail in their responsibility while performing the duties as guardians after the death of parents of Baudelaire children.

Therefore, this study argues that *The Series of Unfortunate Events* creates art-horror through moral reversal rather than supernatural creatures. This idea adds something new to both horror theory and the study of children's literature.

Art-Horror and Breaking of Categories:

The idea of breaking categories can go beyond the body and include morality and social systems with reference to Daniel Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events*. According to Carroll, horror appears when people face characters that break normal categories. He describes such beings as "in-between, contradictory, incomplete, or without clear form" (Carroll 32). Usually, this idea applies to the creatures such as vampires or zombies—figures that mix life and death but Count Olaf represents the wider type of impurity that goes not only beyond the body but also social system. He dresses up as teachers, doctors, and guardians and pretending the role of a noble person that is normally meant to protect Baudelaire children. He takes on positions linked with children's safety but commits harmful acts, he breaks moral boundaries of family institution in which children hope moral, economic, educational support. When children stay with him in his house he comes with his friends to have meal. One of his friends warns the children, and explains the cunning intension of Count Olaf towards children. He says,

“The only reason Count Olaf hasn’t torn you limb from limb is that he hasn’t

Gotten hold of your money. He allows you to live while he works out his plans ...What reason will he have to keep you alive after he has your money?”

(Snicket 90).

Here he performs harmful acts to children and proves a morally corrupted person. Here horror does not come from his physical appearance, but from his moral corruption. Fred Botting explains that Gothic fiction often shows social fears through characters who disturb normal structures (5). Olaf works in this way. He represents the fear that people in authority can become dangerous.

Threat and Continuous Danger:

According to Carroll, a monster must also be harmful or threatening (16). Count Olaf’s repeated attempts to kill the Baudelaire children meet this condition. His plans—burning buildings, forcing marriage, poisoning—are real and direct. They create constant tension and horror in the story. Klaus the eldest child of the Baudelaire knows about Olaf’s forcing marriage to his sister Violet. He says,

You’re going to marry my sister to gain control of the Baudelaire fortune! Or at least, that’s what you planned to do. But when I show this information to Mr. Poe, your play will not be performed, and you will go to jail!” (Snicket 98)

Here the quotation shows Count Olaf’s immoral behavior towards the Baudelaire girl Violet who is not at the age of marriage. He wants to do all these things to gain property of Baudelaire.

It leads the children not to trust their horrible guardian Count Olaf. But the danger is not limited to Olaf alone. The repeated failure of adult authorities increases the sense of risk. Mr. Poe and other guardians ignore clear signs of

Olaf’s return. This pattern shows what Rosemary Jackson calls fantasy’s ability to reveal the weakness of institutions (Jackson 4). In the children’s world, there is no strong or reliable protection.

Carroll also says that horror stories often focus on discovering and proving that the monster exists (99). In Handler’s series, readers recognize Olaf immediately, but the adults like Mr. Poe does not understand the cunning nature of Olaf. He blindly believes him and let the children stay with that horrible man. This dramatic irony increases anxiety because knowing the truth does not keep the children safe.

Repetition and Unstable Structure:

In *The Series of Unfortunate Events* each book follows a similar pattern: the children move to a new place for safety stay with new guardians, Olaf appears in disguise, children recognize that horrible man, try to tell the truth of Olaf to their new guardian but here adults refuse to believe the children, the truth is revealed later on after much cunning and horrible activities of Olaf, and the children escape. This goes on continuously in each book. This repeated structure creates a feeling that events will happen again and again. Unlike traditional children’s stories that end with safety and order, Handler does not give a permanent solution, and confuses the readers. There is no happy end of all the books in the series. Carroll’s model of horror usually includes confrontation and final closure (99). However, Handler challenges this idea by allowing Olaf to survive throughout the series. As a result, the horror builds over time instead of ending in each book.

Maria Nikolajeva states that children’s literature often shows adults as powerful and children as dependent (Nikolajeva 12). Handler reverses this pattern showing the failure of institution of family. The children are intelligent

and aware, while adults are careless and incompetent as they don't trust the children. This role explains the weakness of normal authority and adds to the moral horror.

Gothic Setting and Moral Monstrosity:

In each Gothic fiction authors create fearful atmosphere by using haunted house, old castles, dark atmosphere, trees, fearful animals etc. Even though there are no ghosts or demons, *A Series of Unfortunate Events* includes Gothic elements such as old buildings, dark environments, and secret plots. Botting argues that Gothic settings often represent mental and social breakdown (1–2). In Handler's books, the setting reflects moral instability and fear of the Baudelaire children.

Olaf's monstrosity is immoral rather than physical. Carroll opines that horror depends on characters that cause both "fear and disgust" (16). Olaf's selfish behavior and dramatic cruelty create disgust, while his violent actions create fear in the series. This combination matches Carroll's idea of art-horror.

Moral Horror and Helpless Innocence:

Each book proves the fear of Baudelaire children that they feel towards Olaf and his misdeeds. Their helplessness increases the horror throughout the whole series. As a reader we expect their safety but they don't get it. Not only in the human world but also in the animal clan society usually believes that children should be protected and harming them is a serious moral violation. But the fact is totally ignored by count Olaf. He does not consider the innocence of the orphans but tries to trap them in danger only for gaining property. Jackson argues that fantasy often reveals hidden social problems (3). But Handler highlights fears about neglect, failure of institutions, and lack of moral responsibility in the series. The horror comes not from

supernatural beings but from collapse of social norms.

In this way, Daniel Handler's *A Series of Unfortunate Events* gives a new meaning to monstrosity. The monster in the series is not a strange creature physically but a corrupt guardian who has lust for money and property. The breaking of categories happens in the moral world, not the physical one.

Conclusion:

Using Carroll's theory, *A Series of Unfortunate Events* can be understood as a complex and thoughtful form of horror within children's literature that explores with new dimensions. Count Olaf meets Carroll's conditions of danger and impurity, but his impurity is moral rather than biological. The failure of institutions creates the horror into the larger social system, and the repeated story structure keeps the feeling of fear alive till the end of the series.

By combining Gothic atmosphere with moral boundary-breaking, Handler shows that art-horror can come from social and ethical instability and in postmodern era it exists in the society. The series challenges the idea that children's literature must always offer comfort and safety because children's mind is always innocent and it is harmful to tell such stories to the young children. But Handler has used the postmodern technique to construct the story. He tries to teach children that the people like Olaf exist in the family and society too. His series proves that horror can be used to question authority, morality, and the vulnerability of children.

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